

Rebound effects in circular business models: A review of cases and mitigation strategies

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Supplementary Information

Appendix A – List of Papers selected for review

Table A.1: Final sample of 76 papers

1	Abdoli, S., Kara, S., & Hauschild, M. (2019). System interaction, System of Systems, and environmental impact of products. <i>CIRP Annals</i> , 68(1), 17–20. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirp.2019.04.051
2	Ackermann, L., & Tunn, V. S. C. (2024). Careless product use in access-based services: A rebound effect and how to address it. <i>Journal of Business Research</i> , 177, 114643. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2024.114643
3	Aguilar Lopez, F., Billy, R. G., & Müller, D. B. (2022). A product–component framework for modeling stock dynamics and its application for electric vehicles and lithium-ion batteries. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 26(5), 1605–1615. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13316
4	Alcott, B. (2005). Jevons’ paradox. <i>Ecological Economics</i> , 54(1), 9–21. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2005.03.020
5	Alfarisi, S., Mitake, Y., Tsutsui, Y., Wang, H., & Shimomura, Y. (2023). Bibliometric Analysis of a Product–Service System’s Rebound Effect: Identification of a Potential Mitigation Strategy. <i>Systems</i> , 11(9), Article 9. https://doi.org/10.3390/systems11090452
6	Amatuni, L., Ottelin, J., Steubing, B., & Mogollón, J. M. (2020). Does car sharing reduce greenhouse gas emissions? Assessing the modal shift and lifetime shift rebound effects from a life cycle perspective. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 266, 121869. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121869
7	Andersson, C., & Stage, J. (2018). Direct and indirect effects of waste management policies on household waste behaviour: The case of Sweden. <i>Waste Management</i> , 76, 19–27. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2018.03.038
8	André, H. (2024). Opening the black box of the use phase in circular economy life cycle assessments: Environmental performance of shell jacket reuse. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 28(3), 542–555. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13475
9	André, H., & Björklund, A. (2023). A framework to open the black box of the use phase in circular economy life cycle assessments: The case of shell jacket reuse. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 27(4), 1137–1150. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13408
10	Beulque, R., Micheaux, H., Ntsondé, J., Aggeri, F., & Steux, C. (2023). Sufficiency-based circular business models: An established retailers’ perspective. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 429, 139431. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139431
11	Buyle, M., Audenaert, A., Brusselaers, J., & Van Passel, S. (2023). Rebound effects following technological advancement? The case of a global shock in ferrochrome supply. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 391, 136264. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136264
12	Carrasco Campos, P. A. (2022, August). <i>Circular economy rebound effect in the context of secondhand clothing consumption in the Netherlands</i> [Info:eu-repo/semantics/masterThesis]. University of Twente. http://essay.utwente.nl/92566/

13	Catlin, J. R., & Wang, Y. (2013). Recycling gone bad: When the option to recycle increases resource consumption. <i>Journal of Consumer Psychology</i> , 23(1), 122–127. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcps.2012.04.001
14	Chen, C.-W. (2021). Clarifying rebound effects of the circular economy in the context of sustainable cities. <i>Sustainable Cities and Society</i> , 66, 102622. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2020.102622
15	Ciechelska, A., Matel, A., Poskrobko, T., & Sidorczuk-Pietraszko, E. (2023). Circular economy rebound effect in the context of second-hand clothing consumption. <i>Economics and Environment</i> , 87(4), Article 4. https://doi.org/10.34659/eis.2023.87.4.635
16	Davis, L. W. (2008). Durable goods and residential demand for energy and water: Evidence from a field trial. <i>The RAND Journal of Economics</i> , 39(2), 530–546. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0741-6261.2008.00026.x
17	de Souza, V., Bloemhof-Ruwaard, J., & Borsato, M. (2019). Towards Regenerative Supply Networks: A design framework proposal. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 221, 145–156. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.02.178
18	Dzombak, R., Antonopoulos, C., & Dillon, H. E. (2019). Balancing technological innovation with waste burden minimization: An examination of the global lighting industry. <i>Waste Management</i> , 92, 68–74. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.04.037
19	Fan, Y. V., Čuček, L., Si, C., Jiang, P., Vujanović, A., Krajnc, D., & Lee, C. T. (2024). Uncovering environmental performance patterns of plastic packaging waste in high recovery rate countries: An example of EU-27. <i>Environmental Research</i> , 241, 117581. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.117581
20	Figge, F., & Thorpe, A. S. (2019). The symbiotic rebound effect in the circular economy. <i>Ecological Economics</i> , 163, 61–69. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.04.028
21	Fons, S., Achari, G., & Ross, T. J. (2003). Analyses of the environmental impacts of an eco-industrial park using fuzzy cognitive maps. <i>IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics, 2003. INDIN 2003. Proceedings.</i> , 345–350. https://doi.org/10.1109/INDIN.2003.1300351
22	Font Vivanco, D., Freire-González, J., Kemp, R., & van der Voet, E. (2014). The Remarkable Environmental Rebound Effect of Electric Cars: A Microeconomic Approach. <i>Environmental Science & Technology</i> , 48(20), 12063–12072. https://doi.org/10.1021/es5038063
23	Guzzo, D., Rasmussen, S., & Pigosso, D. (2023, September 10). <i>Mapping the potential intended and unintended consequences of Circular Economy policy measures: The common charger initiative.</i>
24	Harris, S., Mata, É., Plepys, A., & Katzeff, C. (2021). Sharing is daring, but is it sustainable? An assessment of sharing cars, electric tools and offices in Sweden. <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i> , 170, 105583. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105583
25	Jin, S.-H. (2019). Home appliances' rebound effects estimated by a modified nonlinear model: An empirical study in South Korea. <i>Energy Efficiency</i> , 12(8), 2187–2199. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12053-019-09795-x
26	Junge, I. P. (2021). Single Use Goes Circular—An ICT Proto-Practice for a Sustainable Circular Economy Future. <i>Journal of Sustainability Research</i> , 3(1). https://doi.org/10.20900/jsr20210009
27	Junnilla, S., Ottelin, J., & Leinikka, L. (2018). Influence of Reduced Ownership on the Environmental Benefits of the Circular Economy. <i>Sustainability</i> , 10(11), Article 11. https://doi.org/10.3390/su10114077
28	Kagawa, S., Hubacek, K., Nansai, K., Kataoka, M., Managi, S., Suh, S., & Kudoh, Y. (2013). Better cars or older cars?: Assessing CO2 emission reduction potential of passenger vehicle replacement programs. <i>Global Environmental Change</i> , 23(6), 1807–1818. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2013.07.023
29	Kawajiri, K., Tabata, T., & Ihara, T. (2015). Using a Rebound Matrix to Estimate Consumption Changes from Saving and its Environmental Impact in Japan. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 19(4), 564–574. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12275
30	Kim, S., Filimonau, V., & Dickinson, J. E. (2020). The technology-evoked time use rebound effect and its impact on pro-environmental consumer behaviour in tourism. <i>Journal of Sustainable Tourism</i> , 28(2), 164–184. https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2019.1643870
31	Kjaer, L. L., Pigosso, D. C. A., Niero, M., Bech, N. M., & McAlloone, T. C. (2019). Product/Service-Systems for a Circular Economy: The Route to Decoupling Economic Growth from Resource Consumption? <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 23(1), 22–35. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12747
32	Koide, R., Murakami, S., & Nansai, K. (2022). Prioritising low-risk and high-potential circular economy strategies for decarbonisation: A meta-analysis on consumer-oriented product-service systems. <i>Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews</i> , 155, 111858. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111858
33	Konash, A., & Nasr, N. (2022). The circular economy and resource use reduction: A case study of long-term resource efficiency measures in a medium manufacturing company. <i>Cleaner Production Letters</i> , 3, 100025. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clpl.2022.100025
34	Kosmidis, I., Müller-Eie, D., & Delbosc, A. (2023). Electric cars as a path to sustainable travel behaviour: Insights from Nord-Jæren. <i>Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment</i> , 125, 103982. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2023.103982

35	Femke, F., & Van Laarhoven. (2023). <i>RURALIS -Institutt for rural-og regionalforskning Interrelationships between mechanisms of Rebound Effects in a Circular Economy in the agri-food industry</i> . Retrieved November 12, 2024, from https://ruralis.no/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/r-3_23-interrelationships-between-mechanisms-of-rebound-effects-femke-f-m-van-laarhoven.pdf
36	Laurenti, R., Singh, J., Sinha, R., Potting, J., & Frostell, B. (2016). Unintended Environmental Consequences of Improvement Actions: A Qualitative Analysis of Systems' Structure and Behavior. <i>Systems Research and Behavioral Science</i> , 33(3), 381–399. https://doi.org/10.1002/sres.2330
37	Levänen, J., Uusitalo, V., Härrä, A., Kareinen, E., & Linnanen, L. (2021). Innovative recycling or extended use? Comparing the global warming potential of different ownership and end-of-life scenarios for textiles. <i>Environmental Research Letters</i> , 16(5), 054069. https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abfac3
38	Lifset, R., Hertwich, E., & Makov, T. (2024). Policy for material efficiency in homes and cars: Enabling new climate change mitigation strategies. <i>WIREs Climate Change</i> , 15(3), e881. https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.881
39	Lowe, B. H., Bimpizas-Pinis, M., Zerbino, P., & Genovese, A. (2024). Methods to estimate the circular economy rebound effect: A review. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 443, 141063. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141063
40	Luo, L., Portugal-Pereira, J., Takami, K., & Parady, G. (2024). Unintended environmental impacts of private automated vehicles: Insights from Gunma Prefecture, Japan. <i>Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment</i> , 134, 104298. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2024.104298
41	MacCutcheon, D., Holmgren, M., & Haga, A. (2020). Assuming the Best: Individual Differences in Compensatory “Green” Beliefs Predict Susceptibility to the Negative Footprint Illusion. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(8), Article 8. https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083414
42	Maier, J., Geyer, R., & Steigerwald, D. G. (2023). Curbside recycling increases household consumption. <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i> , 199, 107271. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.107271
43	Makov, T., & Font Vivanco, D. (2018). Does the Circular Economy Grow the Pie? The Case of Rebound Effects From Smartphone Reuse. <i>Frontiers in Energy Research</i> , 6. https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2018.00039
44	Medina-Tapia, M., & Robusté, F. (2018). Exploring paradigm shift impacts in urban mobility: Autonomous Vehicles and Smart Cities. <i>Transportation Research Procedia</i> , 33, 203–210. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2018.10.093
45	Meshulam, T., Font-Vivanco, D., Blass, V., & Makov, T. (2023). Sharing economy rebound: The case of peer-to-peer sharing of food waste. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 27(3), 882–895. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13319
46	Metic, J., Guzzo, D., Kopainsky, B., McAloone, T. C., & Pigosso, D. C. A. (2024). A simulation-based approach for investigating the dynamics of rebound effects in the circular economy: A case of use-oriented product/service system. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> , 365, 121627. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.121627
47	Morseletto, P. (2022). Environmental principles for modern sustainable economic frameworks including the circular economy. <i>Sustainability Science</i> , 17(5), 2165–2171. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01208-w
48	Naumov, S., Keith, D. R., & Fine, C. H. (2020). Unintended Consequences of Automated Vehicles and Pooling for Urban Transportation Systems. <i>Production and Operations Management</i> , 29(5), 1354–1371. https://doi.org/10.1111/poms.13166
49	Onat, N. C., Mandouri, J., Kucukvar, M., Sen, B., Abbasi, S. A., Alhajjaseen, W., Kutty, A. A., Jabbar, R., Contestabile, M., & Hamouda, A. M. (2023). Rebound effects undermine carbon footprint reduction potential of autonomous electric vehicles. <i>Nature Communications</i> , 14(1), 6258. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41992-2
50	Ottelin, J., Cetinay, H., & Behrens, P. (2020). Rebound effects may jeopardize the resource savings of circular consumption: Evidence from household material footprints. <i>Environmental Research Letters</i> , 15(10), 104044. https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abaa78
51	Ottelin, J., Heinonen, J., & Junnila, S. (2017). <i>Rebound effects for reduced car ownership and driving</i> . https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315598529-15
52	Polizzi di Sorrentino, E., Woelbert, E., & Sala, S. (2016). Consumers and their behavior: State of the art in behavioral science supporting use phase modeling in LCA and ecodesign. <i>The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , 21(2), 237–251. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-015-1016-2
53	Realini, A., Borgarello, M., Viani, S., Maggiore, S., Nsangwe Businge, C., & Caruso, C. (2021). Estimating the Potential of Ride Sharing in Urban Areas: The Milan Metropolitan Area Case Study. <i>[Journal of Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems]</i> , [9]([3]), [1]-[17].
54	Ribera Jemio, P., Merino-Saum, A., Hansmann, R., & Binder, C. R. (2024). Is the sharing economy a sustainable mode of consumption? An empirical case study of sharing of household goods and environmental rebound effects in a university context. <i>Cleaner and Responsible Consumption</i> , 14, 100210. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clrc.2024.100210
55	Safarzynska, K., Di Domenico, L., & Raberto, M. (2023). The leakage effect may undermine the circular economy efforts. <i>Scientific Reports</i> , 13(1), 16677. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-44004-x

56	Santarius, T., Bieser, J. C. T., Frick, V., Höjer, M., Gossen, M., Hilty, L. M., Kern, E., Pohl, J., Rohde, F., & Lange, S. (2023). Digital sufficiency: Conceptual considerations for ICTs on a finite planet. <i>Annals of Telecommunications</i> , 78(5), 277–295. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12243-022-00914-x
57	Shi, T., Huang, R., & Sarigöllü, E. (2022). A qualitative study on internal motivations and consequences of consumer upcycling. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 377, 134185. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134185
58	Shinde, R., Froemelt, A., Kim, A., & Hellweg, S. (2022). A novel machine-learning approach for evaluating rebounds-associated environmental footprint of households and application to cooperative housing. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> , 304, 114205. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.114205
59	Siderius, T., & Poldner, K. (2021). Reconsidering the Circular Economy Rebound effect: Propositions from a case study of the Dutch Circular Textile Valley. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 293, 125996. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.125996
60	Skelton, A. C. H., Paroussos, L., & Allwood, J. M. (2020). Comparing energy and material efficiency rebound effects: An exploration of scenarios in the GEM-E3 macroeconomic model. <i>Ecological Economics</i> , 173, 106544. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106544
61	Sorrell, S., Gatersleben, B., & Druckman, A. (2020). The limits of energy sufficiency: A review of the evidence for rebound effects and negative spillovers from behavioural change. <i>Energy Research & Social Science</i> , 64, 101439. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101439
62	Sourabh, S., Menon, B. G., & Mahanty, B. (2024). Econometric analysis of circular economy co-flow process in metal industry. <i>Quality & Quantity</i> , 58(2), 1583–1602. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-023-01709-5
63	Spiller, M., Vingerhoets, R., Vlaeminck, S. E., Wichern, F., & Papangelou, A. (2024). Beyond circularity! Integration of circularity, efficiency, and sufficiency for nutrient management in agri-food systems. <i>Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems</i> . https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-024-10339-8
64	Throne-Holst, H., Stø, E., & Strandbakken, P. (2007). The role of consumption and consumers in zero emission strategies. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 15(13), 1328–1336. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2006.07.018
65	Tunn, V. S. C., & Ackermann, L. (2020). COMPARING CONSUMERS' PRODUCT CARE IN ACCESS AND OWNERSHIP MODELS. <i>Proceedings of the Design Society: DESIGN Conference</i> , 1, 2167–2176. https://doi.org/10.1017/dsd.2020.80
66	Vegter, D., van Hillegersberg, J., & Olthaar, M. (2023). Performance measurement system for circular supply chain management. <i>Sustainable Production and Consumption</i> , 36, 171–183. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.01.003
67	Vélez, A. M. A. (2023). Economic impacts, carbon footprint and rebound effects of car sharing: Scenario analysis assessing business-to-consumer and peer-to-peer car sharing. <i>Sustainable Production and Consumption</i> , 35, 238–249. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.11.004
68	Walnum, H. J., Aall, C., & Løkke, S. (2014). Can Rebound Effects Explain Why Sustainable Mobility Has Not Been Achieved? <i>Sustainability</i> , 6(12), Article 12. https://doi.org/10.3390/su6129510
69	Walzberg, J., Dandres, T., Merveille, N., Cheriet, M., & Samson, R. (2020). Should we fear the rebound effect in smart homes? <i>Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews</i> , 125, 109798. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.109798
70	Warmington-Lundström, J., & Laurenti, R. (2020). Reviewing circular economy rebound effects: The case of online peer-to-peer boat sharing. <i>Resources, Conservation & Recycling: X</i> , 5, 100028. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcrx.2019.100028
71	Wiprächtiger, M., Rapp, M., Hellweg, S., Shinde, R., & Haupt, M. (2022). Turning trash into treasure: An approach to the environmental assessment of waste prevention and its application to clothing and furniture in Switzerland. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 26(4), 1389–1405. https://doi.org/10.1111/jieec.13275
72	Yakovovitch, N., & Grinstein, A. (2016). Materialism and the Boomerang Effect of Descriptive Norm Demarketing: Extension and Remedy in an Environmental Context. <i>Journal of Public Policy & Marketing</i> , 35(1), 91–107. https://doi.org/10.1509/jppm.14.064
73	Yang, S., Duan, Z., & Jiang, X. (2023). Spatial dynamics and influencing factors of carbon rebound effect in tourism transport: Evidence from the Yangtze-river delta urban agglomeration. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> , 344, 118431. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.118431
74	Zerbino, P. (2022). How to manage the Circular Economy Rebound effect: A proposal for contingency-based guidelines. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 378, 134584. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134584
75	Zhang, Q., Dhir, A., & Kaur, P. (2022). Circular economy and the food sector: A systematic literature review. <i>Sustainable Production and Consumption</i> , 32, 655–668. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.05.010
76	Zink, T., & Geyer, R. (2017). Circular Economy Rebound. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 21(3), 593–602. https://doi.org/10.1111/jieec.12545

Appendix B – List of circular business model archetypes, and identified rebound effects & mitigation strategies with detailed references

Table B.1: Expanded version of Table 4 of list of circular business model archetypes, their identified rebound effects and corresponding mitigation solutions with detailed references.

Circular Business Model Archetype Clusters	Rebound Effect Cases	Rebound Mitigation Suggestions	
		Business	Policy
Dematerialisation or Sufficiency <i>(E.g., Dematerialised services, Demand reduction services, Encourage sufficiency)</i>	Direct: None reported Indirect: - In the case of reducing car usage, rebounds in the form of increased spending on other goods and services were found, resulting in greater environmental impact (Ottelin et al., 2017) - Re-spending of energy cost savings from smart homes on other goods and services that have a higher environmental impact (Walzberg et al., 2020) Economy-wide: None reported	- Introduce measures to reduce car use rather than car ownership & promote more energy efficient vehicles (Ottelin et al., 2017) - Transparency regarding the true environmental footprint of a product or service, in order to avoid misguided consumption behaviors. This also means to avoid abstract or generic labeling ("green" labels) (MacCutcheon et al., 2020) - Carbon labeling that emphasizes ecological damage of consumption, so as to keep demarketing message intact (raise awareness about consequence of choice) (Yakovovitch et al., 2016) - Pursue regenerative strategies, such as maintaining the health of ecosystems through restoration and remediation, aiming to make a positive environmental impact, while minimizing or eliminating environmental harm (Morsoletto, 2022) - Accounting for the rebound effect in the load shifting of a smart home's heating system (Walzberg et al., 2020)	- Urban planning that reduces travel to essential services, work etc. (Ottelin et al., 2017) - Incentivizing consumers to consistently reduce their consumption behavior on multiple fronts simultaneously. For e.g. reduce the use of cars, aviation and meat simultaneously (Sorrell et al., 2020) - Increasing the cost of energy for example through taxes & decreasing the cost of labor through taxes to promote labor intensive industry (Santarius et al, 2022)
Collaborative Consumption <i>(E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)</i>	Direct: - Increased direct consumption/use due to reduced costs, congestion and travel time (Medina-Tapia & Robusté, 2018; Warmington-Lundström & Laurenti, 2020) Indirect:	- Increase opportunities for consumers to feel attached to their shared products, as owner-occupiers were found to invest more in the quality and sustainability of their home, than renters (Junnilla et al., 2018)	- Medina-Tapia & Robuste (2018) suggest: ▶ Better urban planning to incentivize public transportation use and reduce travel time

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - With car ride sharing, a reduction of vehicle kilometers leads to energy savings, but ride sharing increases number of passengers traveling by car through a modal shift effect, i. e. consumers switch from a mode of transport that had lower impact (e.g., public transport, walking, cycling) to another with higher impact (e.g., car sharing) due to increased ease of access (Amatuni et al., 2020; Realini et al., 2021) - Efficiency leads to monetary savings, which are respent on increased consumption of other goods and services (Ribera Jemio et al., 2024; Meshulam et al., 2023; Vélez, 2023; Warmington-Lundström & Laurenti, 2020) - Savings from lower rents from cooperative housing are re-spent on other goods and services that have a higher environmental impact (Shinde et al., 2022) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Harris et al. (2021) make several recommendations with regard to different forms of resource sharing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ With office sharing smaller office spaces are recommended, as this reduces the need for heating ▸ With tool sharing, reduced purchases and reducing unnecessary consumption is proposed ▸ With car sharing, adoption of EV cars is proposed in business-to-consumer sharing schemes - Holistic assessment of the impacts of food sharing including the rebounds in order to account for them (Meshulam et al., 2023) - Raise awareness of the risk of rebounds among customers and trial non-economic mechanisms, symbolic rewards, information provision and nudging (Warmington-Lundström & Laurenti, 2020) - Shift consumption towards less resource intensive products and services (Vélez, 2023) - Educate consumers about the rebound effects and about the impact of their behavior on the environment (Shinde et al., 2022) - According to Ackermann & Tunn (2024), in order to prevent careless consumption behavior: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Inform consumers about the importance of product care ▸ Design products that indicate the need for maintenance in time and make maintenance easy to access for the consumer ▸ Make the consequence of product care visible to the consumer and raise long-term awareness about the need for product care ▸ Facilitate product care by designing products with automated care functions ▸ Use norms, ratings and other social mechanisms to foster product care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Policies to increase peer-to-peer sharing ▸ Restrictions on private transportation (for e.g., higher parking fees) - Vélez (2023) recommends: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Incentivizing low-emission technology ▸ Incentivise efforts to change lifestyles of consumers ▸ Reduce consumption of high-emission goods
<p>Economy-wide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-operational emissions and lifetime shift effect; when consumers switch to a new modes of transport that increases the non-operational emissions of the older other modes of transport (Amatuni et al., 2020) - A demand increase in car use because of reduced costs, congestion and travel time, would encourage urban sprawl (social rebound) (Medina-Tapia & Robusté, 2018) 		

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Adapt the appearance of the product to each user ▸ Design a product that learns the users habits ▸ Create a product personality ▸ Use rewards and fines ▸ Design products that feel expensive 	
Product-Service Systems <i>(E.g., Product-as-a-service, Rental, Hire, Leasing, Pay-per-use, functional sales)</i>	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Significant decrease in product care for PSS users, due to lack of attachment to the product, which results in higher replacement rate (Tunn & Ackermann, 2020) - Higher consumer expectations regarding the state of the product such that no traces of use are acceptable and products and components become obsolete sooner than in ownership (Tunn & Ackermann, 2020) - Need for maintaining high/relevant stock to meet potential consumer demand leads to rebound (Metic et al., 2023) - If the PSS encourages consumers to use the service more or increase the frequency of product replacement this can lead to rebound effects (Metic et al., 2024; Tunn & Ackermann, 2020) - If savings made from renting clothes are respent on other goods or services that leads to rebounds (Metic et al., 2023) - Consumers have slightly lower tendency to discard secondhand products due to greater emotional attachment (positive rebound) (Tunn & Ackermann, 2020) - In car sharing, introduction of more fuel-efficient cars will result in an increase in travel demand, offsetting the impact reduction gains of the more fuel efficient cars (Abdoli et al., 2019) - If savings made from car sharing are respent on other goods and service, that will lead to rebounds (Vélez, 2023) Indirect: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Re-spending savings made from car sharing on other goods and services leads to rebounds (Vélez, 2023) Economy-wide: <p>None reported</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Tunn & Ackerman (2020) recommend: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Design for care: users showed a tendency to take better care of products they're attached to and product care was positively related to users' long term orientation and innovativeness ▸ Design to reduce the need for care ▸ Contractual conditions to stimulate care or penalize the lack thereof - Make users more attached to a product, thus prolonging its life span, as a means to counteract careless consumption (Junge, 2021) - Make efforts to change the lifestyles of consumers by encouraging a shift consumption towards less resource intensive products and services (Vélez, 2023) - Price control: Encourage consumers to pay more for resource efficient solution, so less disposable income is leftover (Kjaer et al., 2019; Laurenti et al., 2016) - Conduct LCAs that simulate the effect of the product on system outside of the product system, to help anticipate rebound effects (Abdoli et al., 2019; Koide et al., 2021) - Integrate multiple CE strategies within a business model (Koide et al., 2021) - Alfarisi et al. (2021) suggest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ User and stakeholder involvement in PSS innovation ▸ LCA-monitoring of environmental outcomes ▸ Eco-efficient value creation ▸ Increased focus on producing from end-of-life input materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vélez (2023) recommends: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Incentivise low emission technology ▸ Incentivise reduced consumption of high-emissions goods - Results suggests that the negative impacts of rebound effects in the transportation sector can be offset by introducing emission trading rules and by promoting public transport (substitute one product for one that has a smaller environmental impact) (Abdoli et al., 2019) - Alfarisi et al. (2021) suggest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Energy and carbon tax to reduce the magnitude of rebound effects ▸ Cap and trade schemes that place an upper limit on environmental stress

<p>Long Life (E.g., Long life products, Products with life extension services, Reduce, Repair, Modular design, Refill, Upgrading)</p>	<p>Direct: - Repair services that provide vouchers & discounts in case of non-repairable products, increase rebound effect in short term due to an increase in sales (Beulque et al., 2023) - Purchasing frequency for subscribers of repair services was found to be 1.5 times higher than the average of its non-subscribing customers, with the average basket size being 25% larger leading to increased consumption (Beulque et al., 2023)</p> <p>Indirect: None reported</p> <p>Economy-wide: None reported</p>	<p>- Introduction of a reparability index for products that can indicate a product's durability (Beulque et al., 2023)</p>	<p>- Introduction of a reparability index for products that can indicate a product's durability (Beulque et al., 2023)</p>
<p>Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)</p>	<p>Direct: - Second hand markets could intensify consumption for some users who like owning new products for status, by enabling a channel of moral licensing. Buying clothes from and giving clothes to secondhand stores may reduce moral burden of consumption (André & Björklund, 2023; Carrasco Campos, 2022; Ciecelska et al., 2023) - Existence of second hand stores could intensify the consumption of "regulars", i.e. those who more frequently buy a lot of new articles and then give them to second hand stores (André, 2024) - Reuse may lead to less intense use of products, as every reuse cycle entails discarding a product before its end of life (André, 2024) - The perception of recycling as lowering environmental impact increases consumption through moral licensing (Catlin & Wang, 2013; Maier et al., 2023) - Imperfect substitution of primary products by secondary products leads to increase in overall consumption (Makov & Font Vivanco, 2018; Safarzynska et al., 2023; Sourabh et al., 2024) - Increased global demand of materials can cause an energy rebound that offset the gains from reduced primary material extraction rates due to recycling (Buyle et al., 2023; Safarzynska et al., 2023; Sourabh et al., 2024)</p> <p>Indirect:</p>	<p>- Incentivize consumers to spend their saved money on sustainable goods and services (Carrasco Campos, 2022) - Raise awareness about the limitations of recycling, while nudging towards recycling (Catlin & Wang, 2013) - Makov & Font Vivanco (2018) suggest the following strategies: ▶ Promote behavior change among consumers ▶ Improve social perception of used products ▶ Use green design to discourage buying spares. ▶ Improve social perception of used or recycled products to displace new products in the market ▶ Facilitate repairs - Zerbino (2022) makes 4 managerial recommendations to manage rebound effects: 1. Rebound effects should be evaluated relative to the value chain, and be evaluated solely in terms of emission 2. Rebound effects should be acknowledged as a operation and supply chain risk and managed in that way 3. Resource specific factors of resources, such as its characteristics and the demand for it</p>	<p>- Carrasco Campos (2022) suggests: ▶ Carbon tax ▶ Incentivize consumers to spend their saved money on more sustainable goods and services - Aguilar Lopez et al. (2022) recommends: ▶ Policy makers can introduce policy and build infrastructure to enable battery reuse ▶ A widespread adoption of battery reuse could lead to a beneficial synergy with the battery replacement practice that helps reduce the demand for both EVs and batteries. (Aguilar Lopez et al., 2022) - Businesses can aid recycling rates by working with consumers and policy makers to implement recycle and recovery systems (Dzombak et al., 2019) - Implement of conservation policies that will protect natural resources (Sourabh et al., 2024) Maier et al. (2023) suggest: ▶ Discourage primary material consumption, e.g., by reducing the size of garbage bins ▶ Charging unit-based landfill fees</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Price effects i.e., re-spending of savings on other goods and services (André, 2024; Makov & Font Vivanco, 2018; Wiprächtiger et al., 2022) - Secondhand market allows consumers to easily discard new clothes which may lead to increased consumption (André & Björklund, 2023) - Reuse of clothes in industrialized countries is associated with more consumption rather than substitution and is not more sustainable as people simply use more clothes. Reuse of clothes in less industrialized countries is associated with substitution (Wiprächtiger et al., 2022) - Efficiency gains result in increased consumption (Zerbino, 2022) <p>Economy-wide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low price of secondhand clothes may incentivize increased consumption of secondhand clothes as well as greater consumption of new clothes (Carrasco Campos, 2022) - Symbiotic rebound; e.g. because increased reuse leads to less recycling and vice versa, the positive effect of either strategy is offset by the reduced material input and positive effect of the other strategy. Worst case, this leads to decreased circularity (Figge & Thorpe, 2019) 	<p>should be considered when managing rebound effects</p> <p>4. Only encourage product displacement when the circular system makes this convenient</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Businesses can aid recycling rates by working with consumers and policy makers to implement recycle and recovery systems (Dzombak et al., 2019) - Design products to allow for consumer upcycling, such as modular products and encourage upcycling (Shi et al., 2022) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Recycled content mandates or taxes on primary consumption
<p>Circular Sourcing (E.g., Source circular supplies, Industrial Symbiosis, Renewable energy, Using bio-materials)</p>	<p>Direct:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A short supply chain increases the ability to service demand more quickly, which increases sales and consumption and causes higher environmental impact (Vegter et al., 2023) <p>Indirect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the case of industrial symbiosis, because waste minimization requires geographical proximity, it also leads to a concentration of the business. This, in turn, creates increased pollution from secondary and tertiary resources (roads, coffee shops, restaurants), because of geographical concentration (Fons et al., 2003) <p>Economy-wide:</p> <p>None reported</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Siderius & Poldner (2021) recommend: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ More systemic approach to design to better enable recycling ▸ Maximizing the localization of the CE network, and working exclusively with renewable energy ▸ Collaboration among competitors when developing new circular infrastructure, to avoid unnecessary developments - Pursue regenerative business models - a shift from an anthropocentric approach to a biocentric approach can overcome rebound effects (de Souza et al., 2019) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement restriction on the use of cars (Kosmidis et al., 2023)
	<p>Direct:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onat et al., (2023) recommend: 	

<p>Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher efficiency of electrical appliances leads to increased consumption due to savings (Davis, 2008; Jin, 2019) - EV users will not reduce their car travel, even if they have pro-environmental beliefs, since EVs are then considered a "green" alternative, which makes driving them a "good" thing. The EV adoption may thus lead to a higher automobile travel demand (Kosmidis et al., 2023) - Lower cost of Plug-in hybrids result in increased demand and thus higher environmental impact (Font Vivanco et al., 2014) - More fuel-efficient cars lead to higher savings, which can translate to the cars being driven farther (Kagawa et al., 2013) - Convenience and comfort of autonomous vehicles increases travel demand leading to rebound effects (Luo et al., 2024; Onat et al., 2023) - Effort to make driving more efficient by encouraging pooling, may lead to more driving and traffic congestion as driving becomes more attractive relative to other modes of transport (Naumov et al., 2020) - More technologically efficient tourism infrastructure leads to rebound effect due to increased demand of energy, services & delayed stimulation of regional economic growth (Yang et al., 2023) - Increased energy efficiency and use of renewable energy led to increased resource use and a backfire effect (Konash & Nasr, 2022) <p>Indirect:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased production and consumption of other goods due to savings from more technological efficiency of producing common phone chargers (Guzzo et al., 2023) - Energy efficiency improvements and renewable energy use led to increased sales, which caused the company to expand its production, causing a long term rebound effect (Konash & Nasr, 2022) - Full battery electric cars and fuel cell electric cars have a higher capital cost, reducing overall consumption and environmental impact due to less spare savings available (positive rebound) (Font Vivanco et al., 2014) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Dynamic pricing that dissuades needless or excessive AV utilization, and fosters more eco-friendly transportation alternatives ▸ Cleaner and more efficient manufacturing technologies ▸ Ongoing fuel efficiency improvements in autonomous driving ▸ Renewable energy adoption for charging - Educate consumers about the rebound effects and about the impact of their behavior on the environment & raise awareness in order to include consumers in circular strategies and thus reduce rebounds that are caused by behavior (Kagawa et al., 2013) - Encourage spending saved money on goods/services with low environmental impact and encourage consumers to consume less (sufficiency) (Kawajiri et al., 2015) - To encourage consumer spending on products and services that have a lower carbon footprint - if spending on such products and services displaces other spending a reduction in emissions ought to be achieved (Throne-Holst et al., 2007) - Zhang et al. (2022) suggest that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Managers must understand the role of CE in the food sector ▸ All stakeholders must be encouraged to be part of CE ▸ Managers need to develop time-bound tactics to carry out and monitor CE effectively - Use additional profit for sustainable innovation (Guzzo et al., 2023) - Prevent excessive consumption through sufficiency strategies on the consumer side (Spiller et al., 2024) - Improve reuse and waste reduction, for example, through design improvements & participate in international cooperation with 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Business-as-usual efficiency gains can be compensated for with physical caps like quotas or rationing (Alcott, 2005) - Andersson & Stage (2018) suggest that separate food waste collection sends stronger signals of what the desired behavior is, compared to weight-based tariffs (reenforcing a desired behavior rather than punishing an undesired behavior) - Surplus savings from efficiency improvements can be spent in a manner that reduces rebound effects (for e.g. by reducing government debt) (Skelton et al., 2020) - Guzzo et al. (2023) and Lifset et al. (2024) recommend: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Price control measures at policy level ▸ Create mechanisms for the adoption of more sustainable technologies, when they are ready - Policy incentive plans that reward investment in mitigation strategies (Fan et al., 2024)
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	<p>Economy-wide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Efficiency gains result in increased economy-wide resource consumption through reduced prices of input materials (Konash & Nasr, 2022; Skelton et al., 2020) - van Laarhoven (2023) found: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Insufficient substitution of primary products by circular products, leading to market growth and increased consumption ▸ Re-investing effect: increases in profit, result in increased consumption as profit is re-invest in production factors (van Laarhoven, 2023) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> regard to technology transfer, innovation and monitoring (Fan et al., 2024) - Give employees sufficient information, safe working condition and the right to participation to safeguard working conditions (Chen, 2021) - Zink & Geyer (2017) suggest that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Ensure that sustainable alternatives are true, qualitative substitutes ▸ Market secondary goods the same way primary goods are marketed ▸ Use education to overcome stigmas towards secondary goods ▸ Make sure to target satiable demand or make efforts to ensure that secondary goods production doesn't have a big impact on overall prices - Slower modes of transport to and on site may mitigate the rebound effects from more technologically efficient tourism (Kim et al., 2020) 	
<p>General <i>(Studies not specifically related to any particular circular business model archetype)</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Education, labeling, smart metering, raising awareness (provide consumer with more information) (Lowe et al., 2024) - Use of green labeling to nudge consumers, but only as a complement to policy initiative (Ottelin et al., 2020) - Polizzi & Wolber (2016) recommend: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Temporal discounting and feedback to the user ▸ Using default options to guide choice ▸ Using the social context to influence behavior - According to Walnum et al. (2014) Rebounds can be managed only if labor productivity is reduced to compensate for resource productivity or if improved productivity, instead of being transformed into increased production and consumptions is used for other benefits, such as reduced working hours 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lowe et al. (2024) recommend: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Fuel taxes, urban planning, and the promotion of public transport and car sharing ▸ Carbon tax ▸ Taxes, fuel efficiency improvements, cap-and trade schemes, alternative transport options ▸ Mine taxes and royalties. Increasing reclamation costs and exploration costs ▸ Including scrap prices on major futures exchanges ▸ Incentives to direct consumption and expenditure - Ottelin et al. (2020) suggest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▸ Lowering the material footprint of all goods and services, e.g. by phasing out environmentally harmful activity ▸ Taxing non-renewable resources and decreasing taxes on labor and renewable resources - According to Walnum et al. (2014):

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- ▶ Rebounds can be managed only if labor productivity is reduced to compensate for resource productivity or if improved productivity, instead of being transformed into increased production and consumptions is used for other benefits, such as reduced working hours
 - ▶ Taxes are identified as an option, but the authors point to the risk of the new tax revenue leading to a rebound effect

Appendix C - Coding of rebound effects and potential mitigation strategies of circular business model archetypes

The following two tables show the full list of literature used for the review, and the corresponding coding about rebound effects and potential mitigation strategies that was reviewed for this study. Table C.1 presents the coding of the articles collected for RQ1, while Table C.2 presents the coding of the articles collected for RQ2.

Table C.1: List of articles used in literature review for RQ1 with the corresponding coding of the rebound effects of circular business model archetypes

Circular Business Model Archetypes	Case Description	Rebound Effects			Causes	Mitigation suggestions		Sources			
		Direct	Indirect	Economy-wide		Business	Policy	Country	Sector	Sample size & Method	Reference
Dematerialised or Sufficiency (E.g., Dematerialised services, Demand reduction services, Encourage sufficiency)	A study of smart homes in Canada.		> Spending moves to more polluting consumption because of reduced spending on energy > The calculated rebound effect varied depending on consumer behaviour ranging from <0.1% (best case), to 88% (worst case), with consumption as usual leading to 4.7% rebound and 5.1% rebound in the consumption as spending trends scenario > Rebound effect was found to be higher in winter than in summer, because more energy is used in winter and savings on energy are thus greater in winter		Efficiency increases demand, surplus money increases consumption on other goods	> Account for the rebound effect in the load shifting of the smart home's heating system.		Canada	Built Environment, Electrical Appliances	Sample size: 2 scenarios of 100 homes each Method: LCA & Environmentally Extended Input/Output Analysis	Walzberg, J., Dandres, T., Merveille, N., Cheriet, M., & Samson, R. (2020). Should we fear the rebound effect in smart homes? Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, 125, 109798. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.109798
Dematerialised or Sufficiency (E.g., Dematerialised services, Demand reduction services, Encourage sufficiency)	A study of the effects of reduced driving and car ownership in Finland.		> Rebound effects in the form of increased spending on goods and services resulting in greater environmental impact were found: - For households that reduced their driving there were rebound effects of 11-41% increased CO2 emissions - For car owners who gave up car ownership the rebounds were higher ranging from 32-122% increased CO2 emissions with an average of 68%		Increased demand for other goods due to monetary surplus, with high emissions from other spending (such as air travel)	> Measures to reduce car use rather than car ownership > Promote more energy efficient vehicles > Urban planning that reduces travel to essential services, work etc. > Measures to reduce car use rather than car ownership > Promote more energy efficient vehicles		Finland	Mobility	Sample size: 1300 households Method: LCA, calculation of carbon footprints, data from Statistics Finland's Household Budget Survey 2012	Ottelin, J., Heinonen, J., & Junnila, S. (2017). Rebound effects for reduced car ownership and driving. https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315598529-15
Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	A study of the environmental rebound effects of affordable housing in Switzerland.		> Energy saving measures create increased spending elsewhere, resulting in a 15-30% rebound effect > For furnishing and clothing waste the rebound effects are similar > For Food waste prevention the results showed a 19.4% to 57.4% rebound effect		Increased demand for other goods due to monetary surplus, inducing increased spending on goods and services with a high environmental impact	> Shift consumption towards less resource intensive products and services > Raising awareness of the risk of rebound effects > Shift consumption towards less resource intensive products and services		Switzerland	Built environment	Sample size: 38,975 households Method: Random forest regression through machine learning models	Shinde, R., Froemelt, A., Kim, A., & Hellweg, S. (2022). A novel machine-learning approach for evaluating rebounds-associated environmental footprint of households and application to cooperative housing. Journal of Environmental Management, 304, 114205. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.114205

Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	An investigation into the effects of digital food-sharing platforms on GHG-emission reductions in the UK.		> Rebounds were found to offset 59-94% of expected greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction, because of re-spending on other goods and services > 20-81% of expected water depletion benefits, > 23-90% of land use benefit as platform users re-spent the money saved from food sharing on other goods and services		There is a savings surplus that consumers re-spend on other things	> Holistic assessment of the impacts of food sharing including the rebounds in order to account for them		UK	Food	Sample size: 750,000 food items dataset Method: Econometric modeling, geo-spatial network analysis, and environmentally extended input-output analysis	Meshulam, T., Font-Vivanco, D., Blass, V., & Makov, T. (2023). Sharing economy rebound: The case of peer-to-peer sharing of food waste. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 27(3), 882–895. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13319
Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	A study of the effects of business to consumer car sharing on GHG-emissions, focusing on the Netherlands, USA and Canada.		> Modal-shift-effect; consumers switch from one mode of transport to another (reported in CO2 eq, that can be translated to 46-56% rebound based on reported data)	> Non-operational emissions and life time shift effect; when consumers switch to other modes of transport that increases the non-operational emissions of those modes of transport.	Increased use of multiple alternative modes of transport, car sharing offsetting alternative modes of transport (bus, bicycle, train), more intense use of sharing vehicles means cars need to be retired earlier, "changes in resource access patterns"		Netherlands, US, Canada	Mobility	Sample size: 3 case study scenarios Method: Comparative LCA based	Amatuni, L., Ottelin, J., Steubing, B., & Mogollón, J. M. (2020). Does car sharing reduce greenhouse gas emissions? Assessing the modal shift and lifetime shift rebound effects from a life cycle perspective. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 266, 121869. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121869	
Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	A study of the possible future effects on urban mobility and urban planning of autonomous vehicle use within cities.	> Reduced costs, congestion and travel time may increase the use of Automated Vehicles		> Demand increase because of reduced costs, congestion and travel time, would encourage urban sprawl (social rebound)	Increased efficiency and lower cost of travel, mismatch between technology and urban planning Not considered in paper: modal shift effect and the impact on public transport, re-spending	> Urban planning > Incentives for public transportation > Restrictions on private transportation	-	Mobility	Sample size: 2 scenarios Method: Continuous approximation method	Medina-Tapia, M., & Robusté, F. (2018). Exploring paradigm shift impacts in urban mobility: Autonomous Vehicles and Smart Cities. <i>Transportation Research Procedia</i> , 33, 203–210. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2018.10.093	
Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	A simulation of the effects of ride sharing in the Milan Metropolitan area.		> Although reduction of vehicle kilometers traveled helps lead to an overall energy saving of 6%, ride sharing increases no of passengers traveling by car (rebound of 1.5% more passenger km traveled by car) through a modal shift effect		Modal-shift effect where passengers change modes of transport (rebound)		Italy	Mobility	Sample size: 1 case study, surveying roughly 200,000 people Method: Simulation	Realini, A., Borgarello, M., Viani, S., Maggiore, S., Nsangwe Businge, C., & Caruso, C. (2021). Estimating the Potential of Ride Sharing in Urban Areas: The Milan Metropolitan Area Case Study. [<i>Journal of Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems</i>], 9(1)(3), [1]-[17].	
Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	An investigation of P2P car sharing on consumption patterns in the Netherlands.		> Responding may result in rebound effects of 72% and 85% for car buyer and car owner respectively, of carbon footprint through direct and indirect effects in P2P car sharing model		Responding of savings on other goods and services	> Efforts to change lifestyles of consumers, to reduce environmental impact of consumption > Reduce consumption of high-emission goods > Incentivizing low-emission technology > Efforts to change lifestyles of consumers > Reduce consumption of high-emission goods	Netherlands	Mobility	Sample size: Modeling on 2 types of user profiles built upon survey data on car sharing users Method: Environmentally extended multi-regional input-output analysis (EE-MRIO)	Vélez, A. M. A. (2023). Economic impacts, carbon footprint and rebound effects of car sharing: Scenario analysis assessing business-to-consumer and peer-to-peer car sharing. <i>Sustainable Production and Consumption</i> , 35, 238–249. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.11.004	
Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	A study of the effect of boat sharing on consumption patterns in Finland.	> Increased direct consumption > Average rebound effect was 46.5%, with 29% of lessees experiencing backfire and actually increasing their CO2 emissions through rebound effects	> Indirect consumption from sharing, as money is saved and then re-spend on goods and services with high environmental impact > Average rebound effect was 46.5%, with 29% of lessees		Convenience of having access to a boat, budget savings respent on travel that has a high impact (flying)	> Raise awareness about rebound effects among consumers and trial non-economic mechanisms, symbolic rewards, information provisioning and nudging	Finland	Mobility	Sample size: 134 (105 lessees, 29 lessors) Method: Survey	Warmington-Lundström, J., & Laurenti, R. (2020). Reviewing circular economy rebound effects: The case of online peer-to-peer boat sharing. <i>Resources, Conservation & Recycling: X</i> , 5, 100028. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcrx.2019.100028	

			experiencing backfire and actually increasing their CO2 emissions through rebound effects									
Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	A study of the household consumption practices of shared products of students in Switzerland.		> Rebound effect of up to 102% in the form of respending of savings made from using shared products, mainly driven by imperfect substitution and moral licensing				> Increase consumer awareness of the rebound effects > Emphasize environmental reasons for partaking in the sharing economy and endeavour to make consumers identify with these goals		Switzerland	Unspecified	Sample size: 328 respondents Method: Survey	Ribera Jemio, P., Merino-Saum, A., Hansmann, R., & Binder, C. R. (2024). Is the sharing economy a sustainable mode of consumption? An empirical case study of sharing of household goods and environmental rebound effects in a university context. <i>Cleaner and Responsible Consumption</i> , 14, 100210. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clrc.2024.100210
Product-Service Systems (E.g., Product-as-a-service, Rental, Hire, Leasing, Pay-per-use, functional sales)	An investigation of the potential of using system dynamics modeling to anticipate rebound effects in a clothing rental company	> Direct rebound in range from 10-38% to 43-53% due to: - savings leading to increased consumption (income effect) - increased store inventory in order to adjust to consumer expectations					> Guide consumers to more sustainable choices > Communicate the magnitude of rebound effects to consumers to better inform their consumption choice		Unspecified	Clothing	Sample size: 14 scenarios Method: Approach for the identification and mitigation of potential rebound effects (AIMRE), with data from (Johnson and Plepys, 2021; Miura, 2021)	Metic, J., Guzzo, D., Kopainsky, B., McAloone, T. C., & Pigosso, D. C. A. (2024). A simulation-based approach for investigating the dynamics of rebound effects in the circular economy: A case of use-oriented product/service system. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> , 365, 121627. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.121627
Product-Service Systems (E.g., Product-as-a-service, Rental, Hire, Leasing, Pay-per-use, functional sales)	A study assessing the product care of new, second hand and accessed washing machines and bicycles in the Netherlands.	> Significant decrease in product care for PSS users, due to lack of attachment to the product > Consumers have slightly lower tendency to discard second hand products due to greater emotional attachment (positive rebound) > Rebound effects could result from access-based PSS' encouraging consumers to use the service more or if the frequency of product replacement was increased > Access-based PSS could contribute to increase consumer expectations about the state of products, so that only products in good-as-new states are deemed acceptable, thus leading to products becoming obsolete at an increased rate			Lack of consumer attachment to product		> Design products for care: users showed a tendency to take better care of products they're attached to and product care was positively related to users' long term orientation and innovativeness > Design products to reduce the need for care > Contractual conditions to stimulate product care or penalize the lack thereof		Netherlands	Electrical Appliances and Mobility (bicycles and washing machines)	Sample size: 212 survey participants Method: Consumer survey, T-test, ANOVA, Wilcoxon Rank Sum	Tunn, V. S. C., & Ackermann, L. (2020). COMPARING CONSUMERS' PRODUCT CARE IN ACCESS AND OWNERSHIP MODELS. <i>Proceedings of the Design Society: DESIGN Conference</i> , 1, 2167–2176. https://doi.org/10.1017/dsd.2020.80
Product-Service Systems (E.g., Product-as-a-service, Rental, Hire, Leasing, Pay-per-use, functional sales)	An investigation of the effect of B2C car sharing on consumption patterns in the Netherlands.	> Price effects may result in rebounds of 71% and 82% of carbon footprint for car buyer and car owner respectively, through direct and indirect effects in B2C car sharing model	> Price effects may result in rebounds of 71% and 82% of carbon footprint for car buyer and car owner respectively, through direct and indirect effects in B2C car sharing model		Respending of savings on other goods and services	> Efforts to change lifestyles of consumers	> Incentivize low-emission technology > Incentivize reduced consumption of high-emission goods		Netherlands	Mobility	Sample size: Modeling on 2 types of user profiles built upon survey data on car sharing users Method: Environmentally extended multi-regional input-output analysis (EE-MRIO)	Vélez, A. M. A. (2023). Economic impacts, carbon footprint and rebound effects of car sharing: Scenario analysis assessing business-to-consumer and peer-to-peer car sharing. <i>Sustainable Production and Consumption</i> , 35, 238–249. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.11.004

Product-Service Systems (E.g., Product-as-a-service, Rental, Hire, Leasing, Pay-per-use, functional sales)	A case study of car sharing, using new LCA methods to also capture indirect effects.	> The introduction of more fuel efficient cars will result in an increase in travel demand, offsetting the impact reduction gains of the more fuel efficient cars > Depending on the use scenario demand increase is estimated to be anywhere between 6% and 37%.			Improved access and convenience of car use increases the demand, which in turn offsets the positive effect of increased efficiency	> Use a new LCA method (proposed in the paper) to estimate the possible environmental impact that a product will have in the system of systems (i.e. the effect on product systems outside of the product system where a change is made).	> Results suggest that the negative impacts of rebound effects in the transportation sector can be offset by introducing emission trading rules and by promoting public transport (substitute one product for one that has a smaller environmental impact)	Unspecified	Mobility	Sample Size: 1 case study Method: LCA	Abdoli, S., Kara, S., & Hauschild, M. (2019). System interaction, System of Systems, and environmental impact of products. <i>CIRP Annals</i> , 68(1), 17–20. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirp.2019.04.051
Long Life (E.g., Long life products, Products with life extension services, Reduce, Repair, Modular design, Refill, Upgrading)	A study of sufficiency practices in retail businesses in France.	> Repair services that provide vouchers & discounts in case of non-repairable products, increase rebound effect in short term due to an increase in sales > According to one source cited the subscriber purchase frequency increased by 1.5 times compared to average and the average basket size increased by 25%, due to the reparability feature			Careless consumption, convenience of rentals	> Introduction of a reparability and durability index for products that can indicate product's durability as well as its reparability	> Introduction of a reparability and durability index for products that can indicate product's durability as well as its reparability	France	Clothing, consumer goods	Sample size: 26 interviewees Method: Primary and secondary data, semi structured interviews	Beulque, R., Micheaux, H., Ntsondé, J., Aggeri, F., & Steux, C. (2023). Sufficiency-based circular business models: An established retailers' perspective. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 429, 139431. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139431
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	An assessment of the reuse of jackets in Sweden.	> Existence of second hand stores could intensify the consumption of "regulars", i.e. those who more frequently buy a lot of new articles and then give them to the second hand stores > Reuse may lead to less intense use of products, as every reuse cycle entails discarding a product before its end of life > In the reuse scenarios rebound effects were found to increase the two use life cycle so that the environmental impact was almost double that of one use cycle (i.e. without reuse)	> Respending on other marginal consumption > Respending on tourism > Respending on new clothes		Increased spending on other goods and services due to monetary savings, convenience			Sweden	Clothing	Sample size: 2 second hand stores, 71 user surveys Method: LCAs & User surveys	André, H. (2024). Opening the black box of the use phase in circular economy life cycle assessments: Environmental performance of shell jacket reuse. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 28(3), 542–555. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13475
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	A case study of reused jackets in Sweden.	> Second Hand markets could intensify consumption for some users who like owning new products for status, by enabling a channel of moral licensing			Moral licencing			Sweden	Clothing	Sample size: 71 users Method: User surveys and interviews with store managers	André, H., & Björklund, A. (2023). A framework to open the black box of the use phase in circular economy life cycle assessments: The case of shell jacket reuse. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 27(4), 1137–1150. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13408
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	A study of second hand clothing in the Netherlands.	> Buying clothes from and giving clothes to second hand stores may reduce the moral burden of consumption	> Second hand markets allows consumers to easily discard new clothes which may lead to increased consumption > Price effects - increased consumption of other goods (sometimes as much as 21% additional)	> Low price of second hand clothes may incentivize increased consumption of second hand clothes as well as greater consumption of new clothes	Convenience, monetary savings respent on other goods, moral licencing	> Incentivize consumers to spend their saved money on sustainable goods and services	> Carbon tax > Incentivize consumers to spend their saved money on sustainable goods and services	Netherlands	Clothing	Sample size: 422 survey participants Method: Survey	Carrasco Campos, P. A. (2022, August). Circular economy rebound effect in the context of secondhand clothing consumption in the Netherlands [Info:eu-repo/semantics/masterThesis]. University of Twente. http://essay.utwente.nl/92566/

			expenditure on clothes or other goods)								
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	An investigation of the rebound effects and their causes in second hand clothing markets in Poland.	> Price effect & Moral licensing: Replacement rate of 1:1.23, meaning if respondent bought second hand clothes instead of new clothes, they purchased an average of 1.23 pieces of second hand clothing for every piece of new clothing that they would have otherwise bought						Poland	Fashion	Sample size: 639 respondents Method: Survey	Ciechelska, A., Matel, A., Poskrobko, T., & Sidorczuk-Pietraszko, E. (2023). Circular economy rebound effect in the context of second-hand clothing consumption. <i>Economics and Environment</i> , 87(4), Article 4. https://doi.org/10.34659/eis.2023.87.4.635
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	An experiment conducted to investigate recycling and resource use in the USA.	> Perception of recycling as lowering environmental impact, actually increases consumption > Around 300% rebound effect, as almost 3 times the amount of paper was used in the recycling condition			Moral licencing; consumers focus on the positive aspects of recycling, unawareness of the limits of recycling, recycling assuages guilt from consumption	> Raise awareness about the limitations of recycling, while nudging towards recycling.	> Raise awareness about the limitations of recycling, while nudging towards recycling.	USA	Consumer Goods	Sample size: 41 students (experiment 1), 99 restroom users (experiment 2) Method: experiment, ANOVA, Variance t-test	Catlin, J. R., & Wang, Y. (2013). Recycling gone bad: When the option to recycle increases resource consumption. <i>Journal of Consumer Psychology</i> , 23(1), 122–127. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcps.2012.04.001
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	A study of second hand clothing and furniture stores in Switzerland.	> Cost reduction leads to increased consumption (direct rebound) > Reuse of clothes in industrialized countries is associated with more consumption rather than substitution and is not more sustainable as people simply use more clothes. Reuse of clothes in unindustrialized countries is associated with substitution > Rebound effect estimates for clothes sharing ranged from 4,2% (refuse), 6% (reuse), 10.8% (share) to 42% (sufficiency) (Rebound effects estimated from graphs, exact number not available) > Rebound effect estimates for the furniture case study ranged from 0% (recycling and refurbish) to 18% (reuse) and 30% (reduce) (Rebound effects estimated from graphs, exact number not available)	> Cost reduction leads to indirect rebound > Time-related rebound; time saved is spent on other activities		Increased logistics and inefficient business practice (sharing, unintended consequence), consumer behaviour such as more consumption, more spending on high impact products and services and more time devoted to high impact activities, lack of substitution	> Raise awareness in order to include consumers in circular strategies and thus reduce rebounds that are caused by behaviour > Encourage spending saved money on goods/services with low environmental impact and encourage consumers to consume less (sufficiency)		Switzerland	Clothing, Consumer goods (Furniture)	Sample size: 2 case studies Method: Assessment within SCSD framework, LCA and MFA	Wiprächtiger, M., Rapp, M., Hellweg, S., Shinde, R., & Haupt, M. (2022). Turning trash into treasure: An approach to the environmental assessment of waste prevention and its application to clothing and furniture in Switzerland. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 26(4), 1389–1405. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13275
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	A case study of smartphone reuse in the USA.	> Imperfect substitution was assumed to occur > Average rebound effect found was 29%, ranging from 27% to 46% depending on the model > It was found that under different consumption patterns, rebound effects could be higher than 100%, i.e. a backfire effect	> Respending was assumed to occur		Secondary market increases consumption (people simply buy more phones), savings respend on other goods and services	> Promote behaviour change among consumers > Improve social perception of used products > Use green design to discourage buying spares. > Improve social perception of used or recycled products to displace new products in		USA	Electrical Appliances	Sample size: 6576 units of analysis Method: Life cycle assessment, sales statistics, consumer surveying, consumer demand modeling, and environmentally-extended input-output analysis	Makov, T., & Font Vivanco, D. (2018). Does the Circular Economy Grow the Pie? The Case of Rebound Effects From Smartphone Reuse. <i>Frontiers in Energy Research</i> , 6. https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2018.00039

						the market > Facilitate repairs					
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	A case study of the impacts of the recycling efforts of an Italian marble import-export form		> Efficiency gains result in increased consumption		Increased efficiency	> A series of 4 guidelines that aim to help businesses counter a given rebound: 1. "The evaluation of CER should be related to the Value Chain and consider the OSCM (operations and supply chain management) environmental impacts other than emissions. 2. "CER should be considered an OSCM risk due to the transition towards CE and managed accordingly." 3. "The management of CER should consider that the characteristics of the resource to recover and of its demand may amplify or narrow the range of variation of the single CER components generated by the circular OSCM strategies." 4. "Product displacement should be encouraged only after creating the conditions to make it convenient by changing the configuration of the CER components of a circular strategy over time."		Italy	Materials	Sample size: 1 case study Method: Literature review and exploratory case study	Zerbino, P. (2022). How to manage the Circular Economy Rebound effect: A proposal for contingency-based guidelines. Journal of Cleaner Production, 378, 134584. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134584
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	A case study of the resource flows of gold in a circular scenario.			> Symbiotic rebound; e.g. because increased reuse leads to less recycling and vice versa, the positive effect of either strategy is offset by the reduced positive effect of the other strategy, as they compete for input materials. Worst case this leads to decreased circularity	Opportunity costs				Material, Metals (Gold)	Sample size: Not applicable Method: Case study LCA	Figge, F., & Thorpe, A. S. (2019). The symbiotic rebound effect in the circular economy. Ecological Economics, 163, 61–69. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.04.028
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	A study of the effect of copper recycling on raw material extraction and nature conservation in India.	> It is found that secondary copper production will not necessarily displace primary copper production and that maximum displacement only occurs when the primary copper production collapses > A direct rebound effect was found that ranged from -2.57 to 2.16, with large fluctuations over time			Secondary production of copper failing to displace primary production		> The implementation of conservation policies that will protect natural resources.	India	Materials (copper)	Sample size: not reported, data from the International Copper Study Group Method: Econometric modeling	Sourabh, S., Menon, B. G., & Mahanty, B. (2024). Econometric analysis of the circular economy co-flow process in the metal industry. Quality & Quantity, 58(2), 1583–1602. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-023-01709-5

Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	An investigation into the long term effect of metal recycling on global resource extraction.	> In a global circular economy copper extraction could increase by 21% due to increased demand offsetting reductions in extraction rate	> In the "Global" scenario circular economy causes an energy rebound, i.e. a relative increase in gas, coal, and electricity use compared to the baseline scenario, due to increased demand		Increased demand				-	Material, Metals (Copper)	Sample size: data from EXIOBASE database Method: Agent based Input-Output Analysis	Safarzynska, K., Di Domenico, L., & Raberto, M. (2023). The leakage effect may undermine the circular economy efforts. Scientific Reports, 13(1), 16677. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-44004-x
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	A study of the potential effects of recycled material inputs on the global steel value chain.	> A direct rebound, where increased supply causes prices to fall, which increases demand by 4.6% and subsequently consumption					> Measurements of rebounds can help in the development of greener technology		Global	Materials, Metals (Ferrochrome)	Sample size: Global steel production Method: Econometric analysis (Vector Auto Regression) with data from Eurostat Comext	Buyle, M., Audenaert, A., Brusselsaers, J., & Van Passel, S. (2023). Rebound effects following technological advancement? The case of a global shock in ferrochrome supply. Journal of Cleaner Production, 391, 136264. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136264
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	An investigation of curbside recycling in North Carolina, USA.	> Increase in circular rebound with increased municipal curbside recycling programs - "curbside recycling programs are associated with a 7.33 % higher level of total waste generation by households"			May be caused by moral licensing and reduced guilt		> Discouraging primary material consumption: - Reducing size of garbage bin - Charging unit based landfill fees - Recycled content mandates or taxes on primary consumption		USA	Municipal Solid waste	Sample size: 9648 households from 653 municipalities Method: Fixed effect model analysis	Maier, J., Geyer, R., & Steigerwald, D. G. (2023). Curbside recycling increases household consumption. Resources, Conservation and Recycling, 199, 107271. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.107271
Circular Sourcing (E.g., Source circular supplies, Industrial Symbiosis, Renewable energy, Using bio-materials)	A study of industrial symbiosis in an industrial park in Canada.		> Because waste minimization requires geographical proximity, it also leads to a concentration of the business. This, in turn, creates increased pollution from secondary and tertiary resources (roads, coffee shops, restaurants), because of geographical concentration.		Geographical business concentration				Canada	Built Environment	Sample size: 1 industrial park Method: Cognitive mapping	Fons, S., Achari, G., & Ross, T. J. (2003). Analyses of the environmental impacts of an eco-industrial park using fuzzy cognitive maps. IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics, 2003. INDIN 2003. Proceedings., 345–350. https://doi.org/10.1109/INDIN.2003.1300351
Circular Sourcing (E.g., Source circular supplies, Industrial Symbiosis, Renewable energy, Using bio-materials)	A study developing a performance measurement system for circular supply chain management.	> A short supply chain increases the ability to service demand, which increases sales and consumption and causes higher environmental impact			Efficiency gains in supply chain which reduces prices		> A performance measurement system that was developed in this study		Global	Multiple sectors	Sample size: 128 case studies Method: System dynamics & causal loop diagram, Data from Ellen MacArthur Foundation database	Vegter, D., van Hillegersberg, J., & Olthaar, M. (2023). Performance measurement system for circular supply chain management. Sustainable Production and Consumption, 36, 171–183. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.01.003
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A review of the effect of material efficiency strategies on GHG emissions.		> Efficiency gains result in increased consumption, with a rebound effect of 20-40%		Efficiency increases demand, surplus money increases consumption on other goods		> Price control (at policy level according to paper), but idea can be adapted for business		G7	Built environment Mobility	Sample size: Unspecified Method: Literature review	Lifset, R., Hertwich, E., & Makov, T. (2024). Policy for material efficiency in homes and cars: Enabling new climate change mitigation strategies. WIREs Climate Change, 15(3), e881. https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.881
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	An investigation of the common charger policy, within the EU.		> Increased consumption of other products due to savings on chargers > Increased production of other goods due to increased profitability of chargers		Convenience, monetary savings respend on other goods, reinvestment in innovation		> Use additional profit for sustainable innovation > Create mechanisms for adoption of more sustainable technologies, when they are ready > Make policy measure as generic as possible > Create mechanisms for adoption of more sustainable technologies, when they are ready		EU	Electrical Appliances	Sample size: 7 informants, 10 documents Method: Survey, Interviews, Causal loop diagrams	Guzzo, D., Rasmussen, S., & Pigosso, D. (2023, September 10). Mapping the potential intended and unintended consequences of Circular Economy policy measures: The common charger initiative.

			> Increased investment in unregulated alternatives									
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of the efficiency of washing machines in the USA.	> Households with a high-efficiency clothes washer increased their washing by 5.6%, due to the higher efficiency of the washer			Lower cost of washing leads consumers to do more clothes washing				USA	Electrical Appliances	Sample size: 95 households Methods: Households recorded data, field trial	Davis, L. W. (2008). Durable goods and residential demand for energy and water: Evidence from a field trial. The RAND Journal of Economics, 39(2), 530–546. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0741-6261.2008.00026.x
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of consumption of efficient home appliances in South Korea.	> Energy efficiency rebound effect of refrigerators found to be 83-109% > Energy efficiency rebound effect of washing machines found to be -35 to -17% > Energy efficiency rebound effect of air conditioners found to be 14-19%			Income effect				South Korea	Electrical Appliances	Sample size: 4000 households Method: Direct estimation of energy use	Jin, S.-H. (2019). Home appliances' rebound effects estimated by a modified nonlinear model: An empirical study in South Korea. Energy Efficiency, 12(8), 2187–2199. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12053-019-09795-x
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of circular economy strategies and rebound effects, within the agri-food industry in the Netherlands.			> Circular products fail to replace linear products leading to growth of the market > Re-investing effect: increase in profit, results in increased consumption as profit is re-invest in production factors	Growth of circular businesses, failed substitution, inefficiency of CBM	> Interdisciplinary research > Collaboration between stakeholders	> Interdisciplinary research > Implement new laws and regulations		Netherlands	Food	Sample size: 13 interviews from 5 case studies Method: Semi-structured interviews, grounded theory, causal loop	Laarhoven, F. van. (2023). Interrelationships between mechanisms of Rebound Effects in a Circular Economy in the agri-food industry (No. 3/2023). Ruralis – Institute for Rural and Regional Research. https://ruralis.no/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/r-3_23-interrelationships-between-mechanisms-of-rebound-effects-femke-f-m-van-laarhoven.pdf
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A case study of the effect of circular business strategies in a manufacturing company in the USA.	> A short term backfire effect (161% rebound), in the form of increased resource use, due to increased efficiency	> A long term indirect rebound of 25% as money saved was reinvested elsewhere.						USA	Manufacturing	Sample size: 1 case Method: Case study using interviews, manufacturing data and a survey	Konash, A., & Nasr, N. (2022). The circular economy and resource use reduction: A case study of long-term resource efficiency measures in a medium manufacturing company. Cleaner Production Letters, 3, 100025. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpl.2022.100025
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand)	A study of the use of electric vehicles in Norway.	> Cars were found to be considered a very convenient travel option > EV users will not reduce their car travel, even if they have pro environmental beliefs, since EVs become considered a "green" alternative. The EV adoption may thus lead to a higher automobile travel demand			Convenience, belief in EV as a "green" option		> Implement restrictions on use of cars.		Norway	Mobility	Sample size: 1223 users Method: Case study using a structural equation model, data from Regional Travel Survey (2019)	Kosmidis, I., Müller-Eie, D., & Delbosc, A. (2023). Electric cars as a path to sustainable travel behaviour: Insights from Nord-Jæren. Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment, 125, 103982. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2023.103982
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of the environmental impact of different forms of electric vehicles.	> Lower cost of Plug in hybrids result in increased demand and thus higher environmental impact > The LCA result shows negative rebound effects ranging from -15% to -75% in terms of global warming potential	> Full battery electric cars and fuel cell electric cars have a higher capital cost, reducing overall consumption and environmental impact due to less spare savings available		Price effects				-	Mobility	Sample size 3 electric propulsion technologies Method: Marginal consumption analysis & hybrid LCA	Font Vivanco, D., Freire-González, J., Kemp, R., & van der Voet, E. (2014). The Remarkable Environmental Rebound Effect of Electric Cars: A Microeconomic Approach. Environmental Science & Technology, 48(20), 12063–12072. https://doi.org/10.1021/es5038063

Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of how automated vehicles and carpooling can impact urban transportation.	> Effort to make driving more efficient by encouraging pooling, may lead to more driving and traffic congestion as driving becomes more attractive relative to other modes of transport		> Public transit death spiral, leading to both worse public transit quality (due to loss of revenue) and more rather than less traffic congestion, with an estimated tipping point at about 1.25 passengers per car	Less congestion encourages transport by car rather than public transport		> Combine carpooling with policies to make driving less attractive		Mobility	Sample size: Not applicable (no sample) Method: Economic modeling, causal loop diagrams	Naumov, S., Keith, D. R., & Fine, C. H. (2020). Unintended Consequences of Automated Vehicles and Pooling for Urban Transportation Systems. <i>Production and Operations Management</i> , 29(5), 1354–1371. https://doi.org/10.1111/poms.13166
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	An investigation of a vehicle replacement scheme in Japan.	> Energy rebound effect; when a car is more fuel efficient it may be driven farther, thus failing to reduce GHG-emissions (rebound of roughly 100%) > "Therefore, even if emission intensity from the manufacture of hybrid cars is improved by 20%, reducing the emission intensity to the same level as gasoline cars, the rebound effect associated with switching from a gasoline car to a hybrid car cancels out the emissions reduction."			The cost of fuel is no longer restricting consumption		> Educate consumers about the rebound effect and about the impact of their behaviour on the environment	Japan	Mobility	Sample size: 4 scenarios Method: Estimation of Life Cycle emissions	Kagawa, S., Hubacek, K., Nansai, K., Kataoka, M., Managi, S., Suh, S., & Kudoh, Y. (2013). Better cars or older cars?: Assessing CO2 emission reduction potential of passenger vehicle replacement programs. <i>Global Environmental Change</i> , 23(6), 1807–1818. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2013.07.023
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of the environmental impact of privately owned automated vehicles in Japan.	> 29-48% increase in travel demand due to convenience						Japan	Mobility	Sample size: Gunma region, 6363 km2, 1.9 million inhabitants Method: Case study, with data from Statistics Bureau of Japan and the Automobile Inspection Registration Information Association	Luo, L., Portugal-Pereira, J., Takami, K., & Parady, G. (2024). Unintended environmental impacts of private automated vehicles: Insights from Gunma Prefecture, Japan. <i>Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment</i> , 134, 104298. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2024.104298
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of efficiency improvements in the global automotive supply chain.			Efficiency improvements reduce prices, stimulating economy-wide demand - 85% of emissions savings in product-service efficiency offset - 77% material efficiency offset - 7% energy efficiency offset	Increased spending on other goods and services due to monetary savings		> Surplus savings from efficiency improvements can be spent in a manner that reduces rebound effects (for e.g. by reducing government debt)	Global	Mobility	Sample size: 31 representative firms in different sectors Method: GEM-E3 multi-regional, multi-sectoral macroeconomic computable general equilibrium model	Skelton, A. C. H., Paroussos, L., & Allwood, J. M. (2020). Comparing energy and material efficiency rebound effects: An exploration of scenarios in the GEM-E3 macroeconomic model. <i>Ecological Economics</i> , 173, 106544. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106544
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of autonomous vehicles in Qatar.	> Rebound effect differed based on the average number of people in a household with rebound effects from 20% to 29% > This is explained by increased travel demand due to the convenience and comfort of autonomous vehicles			Increased demand		> Dynamic pricing that dissuades needless or excessive AV utilization, and fosters more eco-friendly transportation alternatives > Cleaner and more efficient manufacturing technologies > Ongoing fuel efficiency improvements in autonomous driving > Renewable energy adoption for charging	Qatar	Mobility	Sample size: 330 respondents Method: Causal Loop Diagrams, Multi-Regional Input-Output Modeling, Surveying (330 respondents), Behavioural Analysis	Onat, N. C., Mandouri, J., Kucukvar, M., Sen, B., Abbasi, S. A., Alhajyaseen, W., Kutty, A. A., Jabbar, R., Contestabile, M., & Hamouda, A. M. (2023). Rebound effects undermine carbon footprint reduction potential of autonomous electric vehicles. <i>Nature Communications</i> , 14(1), 6258. https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41992-2

Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of the rebound effects of technological efficiency in the tourism industry in China.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Direct rebound effect in terms of carbon ranging from 0.12-1.69 measured in 2017 > Efficiency gains are offset by increased consumption due to stimulation of new socio-economic growth 						China	Tourism	<p>Sample size: The tourism of Yangtze River Delta</p> <p>Method: Economic modeling, with data from China's statistical yearbook, social and economic communiques of local governments and data collected from cities</p>	<p>Yang, S., Duan, Z., & Jiang, X. (2023). Spatial dynamics and influencing factors of carbon rebound effect in tourism transport: Evidence from the Yangtze-river delta urban agglomeration. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i>, 344, 118431. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.118431</p>
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Table C.2: List of articles used in literature review for RQ2 and the respective coding for potential rebound mitigation strategies

Circular Business Model Archetypes	Case Description	Causes	Mitigation suggestions		Sources			
			Business	Policy	Country	Sector	Sample size & Method	Reference
Dematerialised or Sufficiency (E.g., Dematerialised services, Demand reduction services, Encourage sufficiency)	A review of rebound effects associated with sufficiency based behaviour change.			> Carbon footprint can be reduced if people are incentivised to change their behaviour in order to simultaneously and consistently reduce the consumption of cars, aviation and meat	Unspecified	Unspecified	Sample size: Unspecified Method: Theoretical/review	Sorrell, S., Gatersleben, B., & Druckman, A. (2020). The limits of energy sufficiency: A review of the evidence for rebound effects and negative spillovers from behavioural change. <i>Energy Research & Social Science</i> , 64, 101439. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101439
Dematerialised or Sufficiency (E.g., Dematerialised services, Demand reduction services, Encourage sufficiency)	A study of compensatory thinking and its effect on consumption in Sweden.	Compensatory green beliefs, which constitutes a sort of overestimation of the impact of "green" choices and a subsequent increase in consumption, causing a rebound effect. Inferential statistics used do not show the size of the rebound effect.	> Transparency regarding the true environmental footprint of a product or service, in order to avoid misguided consumption behaviours. This also means to avoid abstract or generic labeling ("green" labels)		Sweden	Built environment	Sample size: 112 participants Method: Survey/experiment, inferential statistics (T-test)	MacCutcheon, D., Holmgren, M., & Haga, A. (2020). Assuming the Best: Individual Differences in Compensatory "Green" Beliefs Predict Susceptibility to the Negative Footprint Illusion. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(8), Article 8. https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083414
Dematerialised or Sufficiency (E.g., Dematerialised services, Demand reduction services, Encourage sufficiency)	A study of how digital sufficiency could be employed to mitigate the effects of climate change.	New technology causes increased consumption and growth, leading to rebound effects. No calculation of rebound effect.		> Increasing the cost of energy f x through taxes > Decreasing the cost of labour through taxes to promote labour intensive industries as opposed to material intense industries	Unspecified	Electronics	Sample size: Unspecified Method: Workshops and a literature review	Santarius, T., Bieser, J. C. T., Frick, V., Höjer, M., Gossen, M., Hilty, L. M., Kern, E., Pohl, J., Rohde, F., & Lange, S. (2023). Digital sufficiency: Conceptual considerations for ICTs on a finite planet. <i>Annals of Telecommunications</i> , 78(5), 277–295. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12243-022-00914-x
Dematerialised or Sufficiency (E.g., Dematerialised services, Demand reduction services, Encourage sufficiency)	A study of the effect of norms and materialism on consumption habits.	The boomerang effect, whereby people who are less socially confirmative react in the opposite way when coming under social pressure	> Carbon labeling that emphasizes ecological damage of consumption, so as keep demarketing message intact (raise awareness about the consequence of choice)		Israel	Food, Electronics, Mobility	Sample size: 515 students Method: Online experiment	Yakovovitch, N., & Grinstein, A. (2016). Materialism and the Boomerang Effect of Descriptive Norm Demarketing: Extension and Remedy in an Environmental Context. <i>Journal of Public Policy & Marketing</i> , 35(1), 91–107. https://doi.org/10.1509/jppm.14.064
Dematerialised or Sufficiency (E.g., Dematerialised services, Demand reduction services, Encourage sufficiency)	A study of how 7 environmental principles could be applied to achieve more sustainable outcomes.	Efficiency principles such as narrowing and closing loops and waste reduction are identified as causes for rebound effects and unintended consequences.	> To pursue regenerative strategies, such as maintaining the health of ecosystems through restoration and remediation, aiming to make a positive environmental impact, while minimizing or eliminating environmental harm > "Efficiency principles need to be supplemented by explicit environmental principles to eliminate ambiguities and distortions & contribute to advancing the science and management of sustainability: - No harm to nature - Maintaining the health of ecosystems - Minimizing environmental damage - Restoring/remediating damage - No net loss - Net positive impact/net gain - Continuous environmental improvement"		Unspecified	General	Sample size: Unspecified Method: Theoretical paper	Morseletto, P. (2022). Environmental principles for modern sustainable economic frameworks including the circular economy. <i>Sustainability Science</i> , 17(5), 2165–2171. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01208-w
Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	An investigation into the sustainability implications of the sharing economy in Sweden.	Increased car travel, increased logistics and consumption. The authors do not quantify the rebound effect, they only quantify the environmental impact.		> Promotion of electric cars to reduce fossil fuel fleets > Policies to increase peer to peer sharing	Sweden	Mobility, Electronics & Built Environment	Sample size: Unspecified Method: 1. Quantitative assessment 2. Qualitative assessment 3. Triangulation quantitative and qualitative	Harris, S., Mata, É., Plepys, A., & Katzeff, C. (2021). Sharing is daring, but is it sustainable? An assessment of sharing cars, electric tools and offices in Sweden. <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i> , 170, 105583. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105583
Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	A study of the carbon and material footprint of reduced ownership consumption in Finland.	Rebound effects resulting from increased efficiency, where time and resources saved are spent in other ways. Easier access to tools could lead to increased renovation. Authors do quantify, but they make no quantification of the rebound effect.	> Attachment, as owner-occupiers invested more in the quality and sustainability of their home, than renters > With office sharing smaller office spaces are recommended. With tools, reduced purchases and reducing unnecessary consumption is proposed. With cars, adoption of EVs is proposed in business to consumer sharing schemes > Sharing schemes needs to be supplemented with behaviour change, to avoid increased consumption		Finland	Built environment	Sample size: 1891 households Method: Extended input-output analysis/LCA with data from Finland's household budget survey	Junnila, S., Ottelin, J., & Leinikka, L. (2018). Influence of Reduced Ownership on the Environmental Benefits of the Circular Economy. <i>Sustainability</i> , 10(11), Article 11. https://doi.org/10.3390/su10114077

Collaborative Consumption (E.g., Sharing economy, Co-access, Co-ownership)	An investigation of product care solutions within collaborative consumption systems in Austria, the Netherlands and Germany.	> Careless consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Inform consumer about product care > Design products that indicate the need for maintenance in time and make maintenance easy to access for the consumer > Make the consequence of product care visible to the consumer and raise long-term awareness about the need for product care > Facilitate product care through design by designing products with automated care functions > Use norms, ratings and other social mechanisms to foster product care > Adapt the appearance of the product to each user > Design a product that learns the users habits > Create a product personality > Use rewards and fines > Design products that feel expensive 		Austria, Netherlands and Germany	Household appliances	<p>Sample size: 86 respondents in the first survey and 9 respondents in the second survey and 5 companies for the interviews</p> <p>Method: 1 qualitative survey, 1 quantitative survey with statistical analysis (T-tests), as well as semi structured interviews</p>	Ackermann, L., & Tunn, V. S. C. (2024). Careless product use in access-based services: A rebound effect and how to address it. Journal of Business Research, 177, 114643. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2024.114643
Product-Service Systems (E.g., Product-as-a-service, Rental, Hire, Leasing, Pay-per-use, functional sales)	An investigation into the product design implications of the circular economy and how principles of circularity can be applied to mobile phones.	Careless consumption causes rebound effects.	> Making users more attached to a product and thus prolonging its life span, as a means to counteract careless consumption		Unspecified	Electrical Appliances	<p>Sample size: 2 case studies</p> <p>Method: Theoretical paper</p>	Junge, I. P. (2021). Single Use Goes Circular—An ICT Proto-Practice for a Sustainable Circular Economy Future. <i>Journal of Sustainability Research</i> , 3(1). https://doi.org/10.20900/jsr20210009
Product-Service Systems (E.g., Product-as-a-service, Rental, Hire, Leasing, Pay-per-use, functional sales)	A study of the potential of product service systems to achieve absolute resource decoupling.	User behaviour is changed by PSS, which in turn counteracts "the resource reduction potential"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Achieve sufficient substitution of high impact products with lower impact products > Encourage consumers to pay more for resource efficient solution > Strategies that counteract the increased spending that results from efficiency 		Denmark	General	<p>Sample size: 4 case studies</p> <p>Method: Framework/Literature review</p>	Kjaer, L. L., Pigosso, D. C. A., Niero, M., Bech, N. M., & McAloone, T. C. (2019). Product/Service-Systems for a Circular Economy: The Route to Decoupling Economic Growth from Resource Consumption? <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 23(1), 22–35. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12747
Product-Service Systems (E.g., Product-as-a-service, Rental, Hire, Leasing, Pay-per-use, functional sales)	A review of the global warming potentials of product-service systems (PSS) and the risk of backfire resulting from PSS.	<p>"In addition, this study identified key reasons for rebound and backfire effects resulting from the introduction of PSS, such as changes in the number of uses, transport, product substitution and lifetime, maintenance, energy source and efficiency, materials and products, and user behaviour"</p> <p>No quantification of rebound effect, but does quantify environmental impact.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Life cycle assessment is crucial to discovering and mitigating rebound effects > Prioritize strategies with a low risk of rebound effects > Integrate multiple circular economy strategies within a business model 		Unspecified	General	<p>Sample size: 13 studies, 1500 scenarios</p> <p>Method: Literature review</p>	Koide, R., Murakami, S., & Nansai, K. (2022). Prioritizing low-risk and high-potential circular economy strategies for decarbonisation: A meta-analysis on consumer-oriented product-service systems. <i>Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews</i> , 155, 111858. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111858
Product-Service Systems (E.g., Product-as-a-service, Rental, Hire, Leasing, Pay-per-use, functional sales)	An analysis of how efforts towards environmental improvement can lead to unintended consequences, and how these unintended consequences could be managed.	Efficiency gains result in increased consumption.	> To fulfill the same needs at the same price, but more efficiently through PSS - i.e. price control		Unspecified	General	<p>Sample size: Unspecified</p> <p>Method: Causal loop diagram technique</p>	Laurenti, R., Singh, J., Sinha, R., Potting, J., & Frostell, B. (2016). Unintended Environmental Consequences of Improvement Actions: A Qualitative Analysis of Systems' Structure and Behavior. <i>Systems Research and Behavioral Science</i> , 33(3), 381–399. https://doi.org/10.1002/sres.2330
Product-Service Systems (E.g., Product-as-a-service, Rental, Hire, Leasing, Pay-per-use, functional sales)	A bibliometric review of the relationship between product service systems (PSS) and rebound effects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Direct rebound effect: non-ownership, adapted user behaviour, changes in consumption practices, socio-psychological factors > Indirect rebound effects: increased efficiency > Economy wide rebound effects: increased efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > User and stakeholder integrated settings > LCA-monitoring > Eco-efficient value creation > Secondary production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Energy and carbon tax > Bonus malus schemes > Cap and trade schemes 	Unspecified	Unspecified	<p>Sample size: 31 papers</p> <p>Method: Systematic literature review</p>	Alfarisi, S., Mitake, Y., Tsutsui, Y., Wang, H., & Shimomura, Y. (2023). Bibliometric Analysis of a Product–Service System’s Rebound Effect: Identification of a Potential Mitigation Strategy. <i>Systems</i> , 11(9), Article 9. https://doi.org/10.3390/systems11090452
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	An investigation into the waste burden associated with different adoption scenarios of LED lights in the USA.	Changing to LED lights may increase waste burdens and if not properly recycled, this will lead to a greater mass of landfilled waste.	> Businesses can aid recycling rates by working with consumers and policy makers to implement recycle and recovery systems	> Businesses can aid recycling rates by working with consumers and policy makers to implement recycle and recovery systems	USA	Electrical Appliances	<p>Sample size: Unspecified</p> <p>Method: LCA</p>	Dzombak, R., Antonopoulos, C., & Dillon, H. E. (2019). Balancing technological innovation with waste burden minimization: An examination of the global lighting industry. <i>Waste Management</i> , 92, 68–74. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.04.037

Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	A study that uses a new framework to investigate the potential of EV battery reuse to reduce the environmental impact of EV batteries.	Lack of reuse strategy for batteries that are being replaced	> Industry stakeholders can plan their infrastructure to accommodate battery reuse	> Policy makers can introduce policy and build infrastructure to enable battery reuse > Scenario 3 showed that a widespread adoption of battery reuse could lead to a beneficial synergy with the battery replacement practice that helps reduce the demand for both EVs and batteries.	Unspecified	Mobility	Sample size: 1 case study, data from OICA, UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs and the International Energy Agency Net Zero 2050 report Method: LCA	Aguilar Lopez, F., Billy, R. G., & Müller, D. B. (2022). A product–component framework for modeling stock dynamics and its application for electric vehicles and lithium-ion batteries. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 26(5), 1605–1615. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13316
Next Life (E.g., Direct reuse, Next life sales, Product transformation, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Incentivised return & reuse, Recycling, Waste Management)	A study of the motivations for and consequences of consumer upcycling in China.	A positive spillover appears to result from consumer upcycling, where the upcycling may spur other pro-environmental behaviours	> Design products to allow for consumer upcycling, such as modular products and encourage upcycling		China	Consumer goods	Sample size: 34 interviewees Method: Interviews, recursive & inductive content analysis	Shi, T., Huang, R., & Sarigöllü, E. (2022). A qualitative study on internal motivations and consequences of consumer upcycling. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 377, 134185. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134185
Circular Sourcing (E.g., Source circular supplies, Industrial Symbiosis, Renewable energy, Using bio-materials)	A study of circular rebound effects in the textile industry of the Netherlands.	Insufficient substitution, moral licensing/moral hazard behavior, environmental trade offs, inefficiencies in the business models	> More systemic approach to design > Maximizing the localization of the circular economy network, and working exclusively with renewable energy > Collaboration among competitors		Netherlands	Clothing	Sample size: 12 interviewees Method: Gioia Methodology (qualitative, inductive)	Siderius, T., & Poldner, K. (2021). Reconsidering the Circular Economy Rebound effect: Propositions from a case study of the Dutch Circular Textile Valley. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 293, 125996. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.125996
Circular Sourcing (E.g., Source circular supplies, Industrial Symbiosis, Renewable energy, Using bio-materials)	A study of regenerative supply networks and how these can be designed to enable environmental regeneration.	Rebound effects are proposed to be caused by a business oriented anthropocentric perspective	> Pursue regenerative business models - a shift from an anthropocentric approach to a biocentric approach can overcome rebound effects		Unspecified	Supply networks	Sample size: Unspecified Method: Design science research and literature review	de Souza, V., Bloemhof-Ruwaard, J., & Borsato, M. (2019). Towards Regenerative Supply Networks: A design framework proposal. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 221, 145–156. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.02.178
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of circular nutrient management systems in agriculture in Belgium.	> An efficiency strategy will impact circularity negatively, as it reduces the nutrients in the system (symbiotic rebound effect) > Imperfect substitution > Efficiency increases overconsumption (direct rebound effect)	> Prevent excessive consumption through sufficiency strategies on the consumer side	> Policy support for CBM experimentation	Belgium	Agriculture	Sample size: 13600 sq. km Method: Nutrient flow modeling, with data from a substance flow analysis	Spiller, M., Vingerhoets, R., Vlaeminck, S. E., Wichern, F., & Papangelou, A. (2024). Beyond circularity! Integration of circularity, efficiency, and sufficiency for nutrient management in agri-food systems. <i>Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems</i> . https://doi.org/10.1007/s10705-024-10339-8
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A review of Circular Economy initiatives for food waste reduction.	Insufficient substitution of primary products. Has some quantification, but does not calculate rebound effect.	> Managers must understand the role of CE in the food sector > All stakeholders must be encouraged to be part of CE > Managers need to develop time-bound tactics to carry out and monitor CE effectively		Unspecified	Food	Sample size: 78 articles Method: Literature review	Zhang, Q., Dhir, A., & Kaur, P. (2022). Circular economy and the food sector: A systematic literature review. <i>Sustainable Production and Consumption</i> , 32, 655–668. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.05.010
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	An in depth investigation of Jevon's paradox and the implications it might have for public policy.	Jevon tried to show a correlation between increases in energy efficiency and growth in energy demand. The conclusion of the paper is that an efficiency strategy for lowering GHG-emissions will probably fail.		> Business-as-usual efficiency gains can be compensated for with physical caps like quotas or rationing	Unspecified	General	Sample size: Not applicable Method: Theoretical paper	Alcott, B. (2005). Jevons' paradox. <i>Ecological Economics</i> , 54(1), 9–21. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2005.03.020
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A survey of the consumption and environmental impact of people in Japan, focusing on savings and respending.	Efficiency gains result in increased consumption, with average rebound effect spending of an estimated 70%.	> To encourage consumer spending on products and services that have a lower carbon footprint - if spending on such products and services displaces other spending a reduction in emissions ought to be achieved		Japan	General	Sample size: 2074 respondents Method: Matrix/analytical framework with data from a questionnaire and 3EID Database	Kawajiri, K., Tabata, T., & Ihara, T. (2015). Using a Rebound Matrix to Estimate Consumption Changes from Saving and its Environmental Impact in Japan. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 19(4), 564–574. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12275
Circular Production & Distribution	An investigation of the social rebounds	Social rebound effects: "Policy changes that bring negative impact on the environment are considered as	> Give employees sufficient information, safe working condition and the right to participation		Unspecified	General	Sample size: Unavailable Method: Theoretical paper/literature review	Chen, C.-W. (2021). Clarifying rebound effects of the circular economy in the context of sustainable cities. <i>Sustainable Cities and Society</i> , 66, 102622. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2020.102622

(E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	associated with the circular economy.	environmental rebound effects while harmful influences on the society including individuals, communities, and social well-being are defined as social rebound effects."	> Open innovation with other sectors to build knowledge as well as adequate monitoring and open information and communication with other stakeholders					
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	An investigation into how circular rebound effects could affect the production and consumption of goods.	Insufficient substitution of primary products and price effects	> Ensure that sustainable alternatives are true, qualitative substitutes > Market secondary goods the same way primary goods are marketed > Use education to overcome stigmas towards secondary goods > Make sure to target satiable demand or make efforts to ensure that secondary goods production doesn't have a big impact on overall prices		Unspecified	General	Sample size: Unspecified Method: Theoretical paper	Zink, T., & Geyer, R. (2017). Circular Economy Rebound. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 21(3), 593–602. https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12545
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of the role of consumer behaviour in eco efficiency and how it may affect the impact of consumption.	Efficiency gains result in increased consumption.	> Consumers should be guided into meaningful environmental choices and enabled to make those choices (f x through labeling), as consumers hold a lot of power. > Rebound effects can be mitigated if savings are spent on goods and services with a low environmental impact		Unspecified	Paper products, energy and waste management	Sample size: Unspecified Method: Theoretical paper	Throne-Holst, H., Stø, E., & Strandbakken, P. (2007). The role of consumption and consumers in zero emission strategies. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 15(13), 1328–1336. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2006.07.018
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	An investigation into rebound effects resulting from efficiency improvements in the tourism sector.	Time use rebound effect, where time saved is invested in other ways, often resulting in increased consumption.	> Slower modes of transport to and on site may mitigate the carbon footprint		Unspecified	Tourism and transportation	Sample size: Unspecified Method: Literature review	Kim, S., Filimonau, V., & Dickinson, J. E. (2020). The technology-evoked time use rebound effect and its impact on pro-environmental consumer behaviour in tourism. <i>Journal of Sustainable Tourism</i> , 28(2), 164–184. https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2019.1643870
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of the effect of municipal policy instruments on food waste volume in Sweden.	No negative rebound effect is observed, however the results seem to indicate the presence of a positive rebound, where separate food waste collection is associated with more recycling in general, whereas weight based tariffs do not appear to have the same effect		> The authors hypothesize that separate food waste collection sends stronger signals of what the desired behaviour is than weight based tariffs (reenforcing a behaviour a desired behaviour rather than punishing an undesired behaviour) > The implication for policy is that separate food waste collection is the preferred strategy.	Sweden	Waste management	Sample size: 3047 households Method: Statistical analysis with data from the Swedish Waste Management Association, Kolada, and Statistics	Andersson, C., & Stage, J. (2018). Direct and indirect effects of waste management policies on household waste behaviour: The case of Sweden. <i>Waste Management</i> , 76, 19–27. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2018.03.038
Circular Production & Distribution (E.g., Take-back & reprocessing used products, Cleaner production, Eco-efficiency, Energy efficiency, On demand production)	A study of the environmental footprint of plastic products in the EU.	> Direct rebound effect: increase in plastic waste	> Improved reuse and waste reduction, for example, through design improvements > International cooperation with regard to technology transfer, innovation and monitoring	> An incentive plan for mitigation	European Union	Waste management	Sample size: Data from 2014-2019 Method: Data from Eurostat Statistic Database, PCA statistical analysis	Fan, Y. V., Čuček, L., Si, C., Jiang, P., Vujanović, A., Krajnc, D., & Lee, C. T. (2024). Uncovering environmental performance patterns of plastic packaging waste in high recovery rate countries: An example of EU-27. <i>Environmental Research</i> , 241, 117581. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enres.2023.117581
General (incl. Dematerialised or sufficiency, Circular Production & Distribution, Collaborative Consumption models)	A review of the methods used to quantify and measure rebound effects.	Secondary production failed to substitute raw materials. Direct, indirect and economy wide rebound effects.	> Education, labeling, smart metering, raising awareness (provide consumer with more information)	> Fuel taxes, urban planning, and the promotion of public transport and car sharing > Carbon tax > Taxes, fuel efficiency improvements, cap-and trade schemes, alternative transport options > Mine taxes and royalties. Increasing reclamation costs and exploration costs > Including scrap prices on major futures exchanges > Incentives to direct consumption and expenditure	Unspecified	General	Sample size: 63 papers Method: Literature review	Lowe, B. H., Bimpizas-Pinis, M., Zerbino, P., & Genovese, A. (2024). Methods to estimate the circular economy rebound effect: A review. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 443, 141063. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141063

General (incl. Collaborative consumption, Circular Production & Distribution, Long Life, Dematerialised or Sufficiency models)	A study of circular consumption habits and their effect on the material footprint of households in Europe.	Efficiency gains result in increased consumption. Impact quantification, but no actual quantification of rebound effects.	> Use of green labeling to nudge consumers, but only as a complement to policy initiative	> Lowering the material footprint of all goods and services, f x through policy initiatives to "phase-out of environmentally most harmful economic activities." > Taxing non-renewable resources and decreasing taxes on labour and renewable resources	24 European countries	General	Sample size: 189,800 households Method: Global input-output model to assess material footprint with data from Eurostat Household Budget Survey 2010 database	Ottelin, J., Cetinay, H., & Behrens, P. (2020). Rebound effects may jeopardize the resource savings of circular consumption: Evidence from household material footprints. <i>Environmental Research Letters</i> , 15(10), 104044. https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abaa78
General (incl. Dematerialised or sufficiency, Circular Production & Distribution, Collaborative Consumption models)	An investigation of the effect of rebound effects on sustainable mobility.	Direct, indirect and economy wide rebound effects.	> Rebound effects can be managed only if "productivity increases (labor or resource productivity) are not turned into more production and consumption and are instead turned into other benefits (such as reduced work time—i.e., more freedom) or by lowering the labor productivity to balance the growing resource productivity"	> Taxes are identified as an option, but the authors point to the risk of the new tax revenue leading to a rebound effect > Rebound effects can be managed only if "productivity increases (labor or resource productivity) are not turned into more production and consumption and are instead turned into other benefits (such as reduced work time—i.e., more freedom) or by lowering the labor productivity to balance the growing resource productivity"	Unspecified	Mobility	Sample size: Unspecified Method: Literature review	Walnum, H. J., Aall, C., & Løkke, S. (2014). Can Rebound Effects Explain Why Sustainable Mobility Has Not Been Achieved? <i>Sustainability</i> , 6(12), Article 12. https://doi.org/10.3390/su6129510
General	An investigation of how behavioural science principles can be incorporated into LCA methodology in order to more accurately model the use phase of products.	Efficiency gains or convenience may result in increased consumption.	> Temporal discounting and feedback to the user > Using default options to guide choice > Using the social context to influence behaviour		Unspecified	General	Sample size: Unspecified Method: Theoretical paper	Polizzi di Sorrentino, E., Woelbert, E., & Sala, S. (2016). Consumers and their behavior: State of the art in behavioral science supporting use phase modeling in LCA and ecodesign. <i>The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , 21(2), 237–251. https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-015-1016-2